

fully mature panicles at harvest and subjected to 50°C heat treatment. The intensity of dormancy was determined by length of time required to break dormancy by heat treatment, and duration was determined by the time required to attain 80% germination at 30° C (control).

Wide variability in germination among control and heat-treated seeds

was observed (see table). Test varieties fell into three distinct groups: weak, short-duration dormancy (NC1281, Seetasail, and OC1393); weak, long-duration dormancy (NC324, Badsabhog, Rupsail, and Kalma 222); and moderate, long-duration dormancy (Randhunipagal, Kataribhog, NC678, Kumargore, and Patnai 23). Kumargore might be considered a fourth type

because it has strong, long-duration dormancy.

Rices with weak, short-duration dormancy may be used as donors for incorporating seed dormancy in cultivars to be developed for areas where preharvest germination is a problem and seeds are needed for the succeeding rice crop. *ℳ*

Assessment of dormancy in some late-duration rices

C. Kundu, A. Ghosh, R. Ghosh, and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, India

We assessed dormancy in some late-duration, high yielding varieties (HYVs) and indigenous improved varieties (IIVs) grown under medium low-lying situations in kharif where mature crops often lodge under water.

Seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and sundried to 13-14% moisture content. Percent germination, dormancy period, and dormancy intensity were recorded. Percent dormancy was calculated based on thrice replicated germination tests (100 seeds in each petri plate) at weekly intervals in an incubator at 30°C. Dormancy period was calculated from harvest to 80% germination. Intensity was determined by exposing the seeds to 55° C temperature for 4 d, followed by germination testing. Intensity was classified as strongly dormant (when it could not be broken), moderately dormant (when 50% was broken), and weakly dormant (when dormancy broke completely) after the treatment.

Among the HYVs studied (Table 1) CN499-160-134, CN499-160-2-1, CN506-147-2-1, and CN506-147-14-2 were strongly dormant: they showed no trace of germination until 50 d or longer after harvest, and were dormant till 80 d. Dormancy broke only after 7 d at 55°C. CR292-7050, CR292-5258, and CR301-3066 were weakly dormant. Other cultures had dormancy ranging from 10 to 32 d.

Among the IIVs studied (Table 2), FR13A was completely dormant for

Table 1. Dormancy at harvest and after heat treatment, and intensity and period of dormancy of some HYVs, Chinsurah, India.

Culture	Dormancy				
	Immediately after harvest (%)	After heat treatment (%)	Intensity ^a	Period (d)	
				Complete	Up to 80% germination
CR292-7050	0	—	—	—	—
CN499-160-13-6	100	7	SD	50	80
CN499-160-2-1	100	5	SD	50	80
CN505-5-32-9	100	91	WD	30	55
CN506-147-14-2	100	0	SD	52	75
CR292-5258	0	—	—	—	—
CN506-147-2-1	100	2	SD	60	85
OR330-40-3	100	95	WD	10	25
OR117-215	100	57	MD	25	42
BIET821	100	62	MD	30	55
CR301-3066	0	—	—	—	—
BIET807	100	68	MD	32	55
PLA100	100	88	WD	20	45
CR221-1030	100	97	WD	10	30
BIET724	100	90	WD	20	50
OR143-7	100	100	WD	15	35

^aWD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

Table 2. Dormancy at harvest and after heat treatment, and intensity and period of dormancy of some IIVs, Chinsurah, India.

Culture	Dormancy				
	Immediately after harvest (%)	After heat treatment (%)	Intensity ^a	Period (d)	
				Complete	Up to 80% germination
Janaki	100	90	WD	35	60
Tilakkachari	100	56	MD	35	57
Agnivan	100	88	WD	50	70
NC678	100	93	WD	30	42
Raghusal	100	61	MD	42	55
Rupsal	100	97	WD	30	40
OC1393	100	54	MD	35	60
Bhasamanik	100	60	MD	35	55
NC492	100	3	SD	45	75
FR43 B	100	49	MD	40	65
SR26 B	100	0	SD	52	65
FR13 A	100	0	SD	65	90

^aWD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

65 d. Other test varieties had 30-52 d dormancy. FR13A, SR26B, and NC492

had strong dormancy. FR13A required 9 d at 55° C for dormancy to break. *ℳ*